

TROCA.CC: AN ENABLING PLATFORM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL INNOVATION IN CALI, COLOMBIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides insights into the development and results of a piece of academic research, which was based around the possibility of promoting social innovation in the city of Cali, Colombia, principally developed by “Creative Collectives” based in the city. The article is organized according to four theoretical pillars: Creative Communities, Collaborative Services, Social Innovation and Alternative Economic Models in order to examine the sustainability of these collectives. The results demonstrate that a platform established to promote processes of barter between members of the creative community for different elements might help sustain the work of collectives and, specifically, the origins of a development process that resulted in the creation of Troca.cc (The Creative Barter Collective).

KEYWORDS: *Social Innovation, Enabling Platforms, Collaborative Economies, Creative Communities, Barter.*

INTRODUCTION

In the City of Cali there are numerous creative collectives, most of which are community-based and whose activities focus on alternative means of communication. These collectives have developed different and interesting ways of combating social problems in the environments where they operate. Their work is primarily voluntary and is not motivated by profit. Nevertheless, some have managed to stay active for over 12 years. The principal motivation of this study was to understand how these collectives have managed to ensure sustainability against all economic odds.

Globalization tends to standardize cultural differences, politics and ideologies (Gumucio, 2003). Alternative means of communication, which emerge from the primary unit of cultural development, represent a clear line of defense against this standardization. Furthermore, these collectives tend to reject traditional economic models (Aguilera, 2011); they should therefore be supported. That being said, this support does not need to be strictly monetary, as their need for resources goes beyond the merely financial.

A theoretical review, and interviews conducted with the Collectives themselves determined that collaboration is a key

factor in their day-to-day existence. As such, this research was carried out in the hope of helping this collaboration grow and encouraging more people to become involved in an organized manner so as to develop a platform that would favour the sustainability of their organizations.

Theoretical Research

The theoretical basis of this research is four-fold, focusing on Creative Communities, Collaborative Services, Social Innovation and Alternative Economic Models. The following section explains the importance of these concepts to the research.

Creative Communities

Meroni (2007, quoted in Manzini, 2008), says the following about Creative Communities:

“They’re groups of people that cooperatively invent and manage better innovative solutions for new ways of living. This is done by recombining what already exists, without expecting a general change in the current system (economy, institutions and great infrastructures)”

That being said, it is important to note that Creative Communities are more than just groups of people that invent things.

They are living organisms that thrive on creativity and on the desire to face up to the social issues that surround them. The solutions that they create are mostly driven by the community itself, and they are designed as explicit responses to problems that directly affect the community.

Following this line of thinking, this research defines Creative Communities as groups of innovative people who generate solutions to specific problems, through collaborative work and the exchange of knowledge, both between members of the community itself and with other communities.

Collaborative Services

A Collaborative Service seeks to create something, be it physical or just knowledge, through large-scale collaboration between differently-minded individuals. Examples of this are Wikipedia and Linux, which are both open source and community driven (Tapscott, Williams, 2008). Collaborative Services usually tend to re-interpret technologies, which is basically, as Manzini (2008) states, the reshaping of existing services and technologies into something that derive their power from people and not from money. In this way, even though most technology tends to be market driven, it can usually be tweaked to serve other functions, such as collaboration.

For this research, perhaps the most important concept concerning Collaborative Services is the Enabling Platform - a kind of Collaborative Service that seeks to simplify the process of collaboration and, as such, augment its visibility and the likelihood that an individual will want to take an active part in a collaborative process. Enabling Platforms need to be accessible in different ways, and not be too time consuming, so that they are attractive to the community (Manzini, 2008).

Social Innovation

Social Innovation is a concept that seeks to exalt innovations that occur in a social context. These innovations usually appear as answers to different conditions of exclusion and abandonment suffered by some communities.

According to Howaldt and Schwarz (2010, quoted in Aguirre, 2011, p. 56), a Social Innovation implies:

“A new configuration of social practices, in a specific context, promoted by certain actors with the main objective of satisfying specific needs and solving specific problems. An innovation is, then, social, when it is known and accepted throughout a community, without any intention of profit”

Mulgan et al. (2006) argue that “Social Innovations must seek to change the balance of power, this means giving more control and power over their own existence to those who are relatively unprotected, thus advancing in basic social and justice questions”

For this research, Social Innovation will be understood as a novel solution, not motivated by profit, which seeks to re-

solve a specific problem and reduce the social breach in a determined context.

Alternative Economic Models

We live in a capitalistic world. As such, any kind of Alternative Economic Model must be different to capitalism. The important thing here is to not get caught up in the idea that it must be in its essence anti-capitalist - it just needs to think some things through in a different manner. Collaborative Economies provide an example of this.

The main asset in a Collaborative Economy is its members, who usually assume the role of collaborators. In many communities, productive activities are voluntary and receive no monetary recompense. That said, this doesn't mean that these activities are based on philanthropy. The members of these economies receive different benefits in exchange for their work. On the one hand, people who work in collaboration with others mainly do so because they love it. Also, taking part in big projects like these brings with it experience, visibility and connections, alongside personal growth and new knowledge (Tapscott, Williams, 2008).

Manzini (2008) says that one of the pre-existing conditions of these economies is that there must be a high degree of interdisciplinary connectivity between members of the community. This should be based on two key elements: knowledge and collaboration. That being said, it doesn't mean that knowledge markets are sites where ideas are exchanged through monetary transactions. They operate more like the Library of Alexandria, in which knowledge is built through the distribution and diffusion of existing knowledge. The product is knowledge, but it's not sold: it is shared in order to develop new knowledge in mind.

Taking into account the approach of the different authors referred to above, the possibility was raised of applying the skills of Interactive Media Design¹ practitioners to find sustainable alternatives for community cultural organizations in Cali. The brief involved designing an enabling technology platform based on the principles of the collaborative economy.

METHODOLOGY

Two methods were employed to carry out this project: the analysis of existing platforms and a focus group survey.

Analysis of existing platforms

At this stage it was decided to work with six technology platforms that support the funding of mass economic and non-economic development projects. To evaluate these plat-

1 Interactive Media Design is a professional training program of the Icesi University in Cali, Colombia, which is especially interested in how design can exploit the potential of digital media from interaction design. http://www.icesi.edu.co/disenio_medios_interactivos/

forms, a matrix analysis using the following eight criteria was designed: Creating Community, Chance of support from the Community, Using media for dissemination and communication, Creation and manipulation of content, Type(s) of projects supported, Method of raising resources, Type of support provided by the platform and Returns made by projects to the community. The platforms analyzed were the following: Kickstarter², TakingItGlobal³, The Young Foundation⁴, Kiva⁵, Donación⁶ y Ciudadanos Activos⁷.

Focus group survey

Data collection involved qualitative research using a targeted survey to obtain relevant information from a range of community cultural organizations in Cali.

To code and analyze the surveys, a matrix analysis of the information obtained was carried out. The categories of analysis were:

- Identification: external evaluation of the collective;
- Project: internal collective approach to the initiative;
- Collaboration: determining the willingness of the collective to collaborate with others;
- Network: relationships with other groups and / or institutions;
- Financing: resources for achieving economic sustainability.

Five groups were surveyed, all of which are involved in creating alternative communication mechanisms in different areas. The following community organizations were analyzed: A Ritmo de Ladera, Cine pa'l Barrio, Satelite Sursystem, Femenas Festivas y La Direkta.

Data analysis

The most relevant results obtained from the analysis of the collected data were the following:

Analysis of existing platforms

- Grant-based platforms are always looking to establish engagement between recipients of funding and donors, creating small communities for each project.
- The most frequently-used media are the social networks Facebook and Twitter.
- Platforms with a stronger interest in creating a united community allow greater access to tools for creating and manipulating content.

Focus group survey

- The collectives surveyed seek to generate reflection in the communities where they operate, by providing information on social problems.

2 www.kickstarter.com

3 www.tigweb.org

4 www.youngfoundation.org

5 www.kiva.org

6 www.donacion.org

7 www.ciudadanosactivos.com

- Lack of financial resources force the members of the different groups to meet their economic needs by other means, such as working in activities that are unrelated to the work of the collective.
- All groups surveyed make use of at least one social networking site as a tool for dissemination. They also use communication technologies as a means of making complaints and demands.
- Collaboration is an important asset, used to exchange knowledge and capital used in the construction of joint projects.
- All groups use free distribution licenses for the projects they use.
- The main sources of finance are volunteering and participation in various funding calls.

Determinants of Design

From the results obtained in the analysis of existing platforms and the focus group survey, the following design determinants for the development of the proposal were developed. The analysis determined that the most important aspects of the technology platform should:

- Enable collaboration and communication between groups and between them and the community.
- Permit users and communities to create and manipulate content.
- Allow groups to create projects, seeking the support of other groups and the community.
- Allow the creation of joint projects.
- Provide the ability to donate collective projects to the community.

Metaphor

Taking into account the theoretical works reviewed during the preparation of this paper and the interviews with different collectives, the following things became clear:

- Enabling platforms that seek to help the collectives are not motivated by money.
- Collectives are willing to collaborate with others.
- Most resources come from voluntary work and loans.
- They are familiar with the internet and social networking, using them to promote their activities.

Taking this analysis into account, it was a simple process to brainstorm practical and pragmatic proposals: to develop a web platform that emulates a social network and promotes collaboration between its members in the form of barter. With this concept, it was possible to encourage cooperation between groups through the internet, while taking money out of the equation.

The main metaphor employed in this design proposition is barter. Not only does this encapsulate the whole concept of the platform, but it provides us with the principal method

of interaction as well. Barter is not an activity that can be carried out mainly in the digital world. As such, it must be linked to something more material; these material elements are the second part of the metaphor, and consist of tradable elements. Three principal kinds of elements can be traded: Knowledge, Objects and Spaces. These categories are derived from the most commonly identified need of the collectives and reflect the areas on which they have collaborated most often in the past.

Next, things must exist that these collectives need and that they are willing to trade. In this paper these are known as “Needs”, (in opposition to “Wants” so that the categories don’t reflect the marketplace) and “Haves”. These elements must be associated with something other than the user. As the platform is intended to help these collectives with their activities, it made the most sense that users should be involved in concrete projects, which in turn would have “Needs” and “Haves”. In this way, the barter process initiates with a project, and not just with a user, promoting the creation of such projects in order to use the platform’s capabilities fully.

Finally, during interviews it was stated that a web platform that involves exchange usually brings up trust issues. As such, the platform should be able to provide users with an adequate way of deciding whether they can trust each other or not. With that in mind, trust is represented by two measurable variables, both community controlled, which are:

- **Commendations:** users can be commended by other users.
- **Barter Reviews:** both parties should review every aspect of the barter process once it has ended. This review consists both of a numerical value and a text review, which are made public through a user’s profile to everybody in the community.

The Digital Bartering Process

Once a user has created an account on the website, he/she needs to follow certain steps in order to engage in a successful bartering process. This process is quite open and user-defined, because that is how the collectives prefer it. The steps that a user has to follow for an effective bartering transaction are as follows:

- *Create some Haves:* users must always have things they’re willing to exchange before they can ask for something they Need. Otherwise, the barter metaphor would be completely void.
- *Create a Project:* the platform is project oriented. This means that everything should start, and end, with a project. It is not intended to be a marketplace based on barter, so the creation of projects is an indispensable process. This includes defining the Needs of the project, and adding the user’s Haves to it.
- *Find an adequate bartering partner:* this includes defining if the other user is trustworthy or not, by means of the variables mentioned above (reviews and commendations). It also involves the existence of a positive combi-

nation of Needs and Haves between the two users, to ensure the process is mutually satisfactory.

- *Define the terms of the barter:* both users have a chance to communicate with each other in order to define important terms in the barter, such as timeframes, duration of the barter in the case of a lease, location of the other user and possible meeting places, etc. The adequate definition of these elements is almost mandatory if an effective barter is to take place.
- *Barter:* the actual bartering process. This is usually done outside the digital world, so the platform exerts no control.
- *Finish the barter and review the process:* both users must mark the bartering process as finished, and then proceed to review the other user.

Users

The platform has three types of users:

- *Anonymous Users:* these may browse and view content. Their role in the ecosystem of the platform is to support project visibility.
- *Registered Users without projects:* these have access to the entire platform. They can search, see and comment on content such as news and can propose trades if they have registered some “Haves” on the platform
- *Registered Users with projects:* as with the above users, these can also register “Needs” in the project. They form the engine room of the community, since the projects are the focus of the interactions between developers and the site of real collaboration.

Architecture

The information architecture designed for the project is presented in Figure 1.

Technical Development

In the technical development of the platform the following tools were used and the following requirements taken into account:

Software

- Netbeans, one of several available free and open environment that allows development in Java programming language.
- JavaServer Faces (JSF) tool for creating user interfaces for web applications.

Customer requirements:

- Modern Browser that allows the correct display of the platform (Chrome, Opera, Firefox, Safari, Internet Explorer 9 +)
- HTML5
- Javascript
- CSS3

Figure 1: Platform Architecture

Other requirements

- Hosting must be on a dedicated server that hosts the database and application, with a minimum 6 GB of RAM, at least 500 GB of free memory, ports 3306, 8080, 8090, 4848, 8091 and 8191, enabled Intel Xeon 5130@2.00GHZ processor and remote access to the server

Usability Testing

Methodology: Using printed wireframes to create a paper prototype, four users were asked to perform certain actions, using their finger as the mouse. The number of errors committed before the action was carried out was noted. Users were also interviewed about how they viewed the process.

User tests

Methodology: During the process of development and programming of the website, four iterations of user testing were performed, as a closed beta test with five users each. Tests focused on the overall usability of the site and the proper functioning of processes.

RESULTS

This research explored ways of increasing the sustainability of community cultural organizations in the city of Cali. We found that these organizations generally sustained their activities by relying on volunteer work, sharing, and accessing finance from government and other sources. The groups expressed the need for free, self-managed tools to ensure harmony with their ideological stance and their organizational guidelines and practices. The proposal involved the design of a technology platform based on a collaborative economy that

would promote the exchange of the spaces, objects, knowledge and assets that sustain these organizations. Although the platform does not directly involve economic exchanges, these can be managed through the platform. One of the main assets of the platform is trust, which constitutes the real heart of barter. The platform was designed and developed using free software, so administration and management must be undertaken by members of the community. The platform is not intended to act as yet another social network, which is why social networking (Facebook and Twitter) functions are associated with it.

Although the platform is in a functional Beta version, the groups have participated in the design, and it is expected that they will also take part in the use and consolidation of the platform as a tool that contributes to the sustainability of community cultural organizations in Cali.

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